

Mitigating Impact of Risk Factors in the Management of TETFund Building Projects

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This study investigates the risk factors affecting the management of Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) building projects in the South East region of Nigeria, focusing on Enugu, Anambra, and Imo states. Through a detailed analysis of findings, it was revealed that several risk factors significantly impact project management processes. Notably, the prequalification of consultants emerged as a crucial factor, with a high mean response value of 4.23, indicating its paramount importance. Other prominent risk factors include changes in project scope, poor information flow between parties, lack of coordination at pre-contract stages, and financial difficulties faced by contractors. The study concludes by emphasizing the necessity of understanding and addressing these risk factors to enhance the success of TETFund building projects. It suggests the development of a robust policy framework to guide project management outcomes, emphasizing the importance of risk mitigation strategies. Furthermore, the study recommends that project stakeholders, including clients and contractors, should collaboratively assess and allocate risks during the tendering process. Effective risk allocation and mitigation strategies are essential to achieve value for money and ensure the successful completion of TETFund building projects. Additionally, adequate financial and material resources must be provided by TETFund to enable the implementation of risk response/mitigation measures.

ABSTRACT

Keywords: TETFund Building Projects; Risk Factors; Project Management; Mitigation Strategies; South East

Introduction

Risk is generally used to refer to a situation where the outcome is uncertain and there is a possibility of loss. The loss is random in nature; it is not intentional. In insurance, risk is also identified with peril which may cause the loss (Odeh and Battaineh, 2012). Thomas (2016) opined that the word 'peril' is used to describe any event such as fire, flood, earthquake, which could lead to economic loss. The uncertainty about its happening, its frequency and severity is referred to as risk. Thus, risk has also been defined as the inability to accurately predict the effects of the future events.

Construction industry like many other industries is subject to more risk due to the unique features and complexity of construction activities, such as long period, complicated processes, abominable environment, financial intensity and dynamic organization structures. Many Nigeria government project construction delivery delays present worse-case scenarios than the Opera House and Scottish Parliament project portrayed. Hillson and Hullet (2014) observed that seven (7) out of ten (10) projects in Nigeria suffer delays with the huge drag on costs. These create great loss of value adding to the national economy and wasteful application of scarce tax payers' money, and disproportionate allocation to meet diverse sectional needs of the economy (Holmes, 2005). They militate against the realization of the planned Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Gross National Product (GNP) growth targets by extension the achievement of economic recovery and grown plans of the various governments of Nigeria. These cause delay in construction especially in Nigeria state/ public sector projects, critical development impending factors that deserve serious frequent investigation. This informs the trust of this research.

In Plateau State, Mangvwat, Ewuga and Izam (2018) reported that all the 23 building projects in three tertiary institutions in the state constructed and completed under funds intervention programme between 2005 and 2014 suffered time overrun while 5 out of the 23 suffered cost overrun. In Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, from 2009 – 2011, Gambo, et al. (2017) carried a research and reported that delay in progress payment, materials price escalation, shortage of materials and low technical skill of the project leaders were the leading risk factors responsible for the poor project delivery. The following significant risk factors contribute to project risk, cost overrun, time overrun and project abandonment, poor planning, insufficient funding, inflation, interest rate, contractors' bankruptcy, change in project scope, political factors, client death or change in government or administration, payment delay, and incompetent project management.

The study is intentioned to address problems relating to the risk factors associated with TETFund projects in Nigeria. Despite the firm contract nature of TETFund, the projects still suffer time overrun and cost overrun thereby depriving the government benefiting institution and the people of south east the value of the federal government intervention in those institutions. Secondly, projects are abandoned, thereby leading to litigations or arbitration, or finding a solution to the problems on site. These create great loss of value, adding to the national economy and wasteful application of scarce tax payers' money and disproportionate allocation to meet diverse sectional needs of the economy. According to Isiofia and Ajaelu (2022), the following significant causes of project cost overrun delays or abandonment; insufficient planning, insufficient funding, inflation, contractor bankruptcy, change in project scope, political factors, client death, risk in payment, and incompetent project manager. On this premise, there is a need to develop a framework for mitigating all these risk factors in the management of TETFund building projects especially in South East which will serve as a holistic approach to schools.

Research Objectives

The broad aim of the study is to examine mitigating impact of risk factors in the management of TETFund building projects between 2012 – 2022 in parts of South East Nigeria in order to achieve successful completion of the project. Therefore, the objective of the study is to identified major risk factors that mitigate TETFund building projects in parts of South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

- i. To identify the risk factors in the management of TETFund building projects in parts of South East between 2012 to 2022.
- ii. To evaluate the impact of these risk factors in management outcome of TETFundin parts of South East, Nigeria

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses was formulated to guide the findings of the study;

- i. Risk factors have a significant impact on the management of TETFund building projects in parts of South East, Nigeria.

Scope and Significance of the Study

The study is limited to the TETFund construction projects in state universities, Enugu, Ebonyi and Anambra all in South East, Nigeria. Also considered is one federal polytechnic in Anambra, with one state owned polytechnic in Enugu. This study focuses on mitigating the impact of risk factors in management of TETFund building projects in parts of South East Nigeria for a period of ten (10) years spanning through 2012 to 2022.

This study benefits society, businesses, professionals, and future research by offering recommendations to mitigate risks. It aids society by providing guidance, assists the construction industry in future planning, and serves as a reference material for professionals in teaching and research.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Risk

In the definition of risk, many explanations and definitions of risk and risk management have been recently developed and thus it is difficult to choose one which is always true. Each author provided its perception of what risk means and how to manage it. Ahmad, Ahmad and Saram (2019) hold the view that risk and opportunities are complementary in their nature i.e., every risk can be regarded as an opportunity and every opportunity has an associated risk. According to Akintoye and MacLeod (2017), risk is a stage where there is lack of information, but by looking at past experience, it is easier to predict the future. Augie and Kreiner (2010) defines risk as the statement of what may arise from the lack of knowledge. Odeyinka (2010) define risk as the likelihood of an unfavourable incident occurring to a project. Hence, risk is defined as uncertainty inherent in plans and the possibility of something happening that can affect the prospects of achieving project goals.

Risk Management

Risk management is a crucial component of the decision-making process for a construction firm in order to increase the likelihood of success and minimize these potential hazards linked with these building construction projects. By preventing future losses or damages, the discipline of risk management seeks to safeguard an organization's assets, reputation, and financial success (Akintoye and McLeod, 2017). One of the nine knowledge areas promoted by the Project Management Institute is risk management. The other eight are integration management, scope management, time management, cost management, quality management, human resource management, communications management, and procurement management. While Williams (2022) describes project risk management as an integrated process that includes activities to identify project uncertainty, estimate their impact, analyze their interactions, control them in the execution stage, and even provide for project risk management, Zou et al. (2007) define risk management in the construction project management context as a systematic way of identifying, analyzing, and dealing with risk as associated with a project with an aim to achieve the project objectives.

Risk Identification in Construction Delivery

Project management (PM), which includes risk management (RM) as one of its core knowledge areas, has gained popularity in the construction sector. Construction projects are failing, according to Mahamid (2013), due to common hazards. Failure rates have occasionally increased to around 6–7% of contract expenditures, with projects in Africa failing 90% of the time (Egbu & Sidawi, 2011; Van Olden, 2014). As a result, RM has emerged as a key component of project management. Effective project managers use risk management procedures (RMP) to address obstacles that stand in the way of their goals and objectives. By working with PM experts and attending RM training, they continuously learn about good RM techniques.

Challenges facing Construction Industry

The majority of issues with infrastructure projects, according to Issa, Emsley, and Kirkham (2012), are caused by frequently recognized construction hazards. Taroun, Yang and Lowe (2011) emphasize the well-known view that “no construction is risk-free.” However, the risk could be managed, minimised, shared, transferred or accepted. In a project context, risks are thus exposed to a variety of control measures. Because projects are difficult, RM expertise and experience are essential management tools (Ameh & Odusami, 2014; Nicholas & Steyn, 2011). The issues specific to projects in Lesotho are listed in Table 1 below. The implications of time and expense are highlighted by these factors. In public construction projects, dangers have been recognized as main project risks (Ntsukunyane, 2015). In poor nations, building is frequently fraught with risk. Risks cause cost overruns in construction projects in addition to having an influence on the progress of the job (African Development Bank Group, 2011), however using risk management procedures (RMPs) may help to remedy the problem. RMPs are not widely used on building projects.

Risk Factors

Research from multiple countries has pinpointed critical risk factors in construction projects. In Saudi Arabia, concerns revolve around drawing approval, contractor progress, and payment issues (Assaf et al., 1995). Hong Kong's challenges include inadequate site management and decision-making. In Jordan, issues range from designer problems to economic circumstances (Al-Momani, 2000). Ghana faces risks such as payment delays and material shortages. Financial matters dominate in Egypt and Malaysia. Pakistani projects are vulnerable to natural disasters and financial woes. Indian projects grapple with labor shortages and material delivery risks (Desai and Bhatt, 2013). Turkish projects face planning and scheduling challenges, price fluctuations, and rework issues (Gunduz et al., 2013).

Theoretical Framework

The organization's other management operations and the management of risks are connected by the risk management framework. As a result, such frameworks must be included into the organization's overall strategy as well as its rules and procedures. The efficacy of the management framework, which provides the foundations and arrangements that will embed risk management across the business at all levels, depends on this for the success of risk management.

In particular, the risk management framework should ensure:

1. continual improvement
2. full accountability for risks
3. application of risk management in all decision making
4. clear and continual communications
5. full integration in the *organization* governance structure.

A framework for managing risk should place a strong emphasis on continuous improvement of management in general and the management of risk in particular. To do this, performance goals should be set, and processes, systems, resources, capabilities, and competencies should be measured, reviewed, and adjusted. The primary contrast between just bureaucratic management and successful management is this emphasis on continuous improvement. In order to do this, the organization's total performance evaluation system, which includes both departments and individuals, should include a component that assesses the effectiveness of risk management. The performance measures and indicators chosen must reflect the organization's goals and be appropriate for the various levels of activity.

Risk accountability must be clearly stated, completely defined, and widely recognized. This includes responsibility for risk controls and treatment. To do this, those in charge should possess the knowledge and skills necessary to recognize, assess, and specify risk management strategies. These people ought to be equipped with the tools necessary for risk monitoring, control verification, treatment implementation, and reporting and sharing of risk management outcomes. In order for people to successfully take their obligations, the business should also allocate authority, provide the essential time for risk management tasks and activities, as well as give the necessary training. Regardless of their importance or relevance, all organizational decision-making processes must expressly take risks

and the application of risk management into account. Records proving risks have been discussed during important decision-making processes must be kept, whether the discussion took place informally (such as during a meeting) or by fully implementing the risk management process outlined in the International Standard Organization (ISO) 31000:2009 standard.

The first viewpoint separates risk management as a distinct supplementary responsibility in some way. The second viewpoint is more appropriate for industries like insurance. The researcher believes that risk management should be included for the building business in accordance with the most recent viewpoint. The ultimate objectives of risk management may be summed up as follows: provide the organization a current, accurate, and thorough understanding of the risk in their operations; guarantee that the company's level of risk is compatible with the limitations established.

Empirical Review

Zou et al. (2005) conducted research to identify key risks in construction projects from stakeholder and life cycle perspectives. They assessed the likelihood and impact of various risks and identified twenty key risks, including issues such as tight project schedules, design variations, delays in administrative approvals, high quality expectations, and shortage of skilled labor. Risks were primarily related to clients, designers, and contractors, with fewer related to subcontractors/suppliers, government bodies, and external factors.

Ehsan et al. (2010) used a questionnaire and literature review to explore risks in Pakistan's construction sector. They found limited use of risk management procedures and analysis due to a lack of expertise. Commonly employed techniques were risk transfer and elimination, which were associated with project complexities and poor outcomes. They recommended formal and informal training on risk management for industry professionals and integrating construction project management education into formal curricula, alongside industry-specific training for construction teams.

Vitor, Nuno, and Luís Alves Dias (2012) examined Risk Management Frameworks in the Construction Industry. Despite increased interest in risk management within building projects, there has been limited focus on constructing a framework to support risk management procedures. The ISO 31000:2009 standard emphasizes the importance of such frameworks. This article proposes a tailored risk management framework for the construction industry, considering its distinct characteristics and the need to integrate risk management into overall management systems.

Odeyinka et al. (2017) examined pre- and post-contract risk variables in Nigerian construction, finding design, estimating, tendering, and assessment risks prevalent pre-contract, and financial, political, contractual, logistic, legal, and environmental risks post-contract. Their study broadened beyond occurrence probabilities, considering management applications and challenges, though focusing on select risk variables.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed survey research design and data collected was cross sectional data. This is a particular type of research design where the primary type of data collection is by survey. In this study design surveys are used as a tool by researchers to gain a greater understanding about individual or group perspectives related to a particular concept or topic of interest.

Population and Sampling

The study population comprises government officials and professionals (Architects, Engineers, Quantity Surveyors, Builders, Consultants, Contractors and the operatives who are involved in the construction of projects). These are professionals working in TETFund projects in Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Anambra State University Uli, Institute of Management and Technology (IMT), Enugu and Federal Polytechnic Oko, Anambra State.

The purposive sampling techniques (non-probability sampling techniques) was used in the study. Respondents were selected based on availability and willingness to participate in the study. Purposive sampling also known as

judgmental, selective or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys.

Method of Analysis

Data collated was analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26. Two types of statistical tools were employed in this study, descriptive and inferential statistics. P values less than 0.05 level of significance were regarded as significant. Results were presented in tables. The descriptive statistics employed include Frequency and percentages for summarizing categorical variables, means and standard deviations for continuous variables. Mean responses were calculated for Likert scales and a mean response greater than the average of the 5-likert scale (criterion mean of 3) was regarded as a positive response and vice-versa. The inferential statistics employed for testing the hypotheses were Factor Analysis and Linear regression.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Socio-Demographic Statistics of the Respondents

The socio-demographic statistics of the respondents include the gender, position, age group, year of experience, field/discipline and academic qualification. The socio-demographic descriptive result of the genders respondents indicates that about 77% of the total respondents are male while the 23% are females. This result therefore, uncovered that there are more male than females in the study.

The respondents revealed that about 8% of the total respondents are 30 – 34 years, 7.8 are 35 – 39 years of age, 15.5% are 40 – 44 years of age, 13.5% are 45 – 49 years of age, 28.5% are 50 – 54 years of age, 18% are 55 – 59 years of age, while 8.8% are 60 and above years. Hence, their perceptions are worth using for general conclusion.

The educational attainment of the respondents used for the study shows that majority of them are MSc holders, particularly, 236 (59%) are MSc holders, 75 (18.8%) are HND holders, 50 (12.5%) are PhD holders while 39 (9.8%) are B.Sc holders. Generally, the academic distribution is normal as it cuts across almost all academic attainment in right proportion for meaningful exercise/study.

Furthermore, about 219 (55%) of the professional are registered with their various professional bodies, while 181 (45%) of the professionals are yet to register with their various bodies. However, 55% of the registered professional is a proportionate representation from all the relevant disciplines in the study area. Also, the data show that 81.5% of them are career condition of service while 17% are tenured, 17% is acting and those on secondment is about 5% of the total respondents.

Data Analysis

This section details analysis on the first objective of the study;

Table 1: Analysis of objective two: Factors affecting the management of TETFund projects in South East Nigeria

S/N		STRONGLY DISAGREE N (%)	DISAGREE N (%)	NEUTRAL N (%)	AGREE N (%)	STRONGLY AGREE N (%)	MEAN ± SD
1	Lack of due diligence in prequalification of consultants at the early stage	0 (0.0)	8 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	283 (70.8)	109 (27.3)	4.23 ± 0.55
2	Change in the scope of the project	19 (4.8)	38 (9.5)	72 (18.0)	229 (57.3)	42 (10.5)	3.59 ± 0.96
3	Poor information flow between parties	6 (1.5)	4 (1.0)	43 (10.8)	261 (65.3)	86 (21.5)	4.04 ± 0.70
4	Lack of coordination at pre-contract stage	0 (0.0)	40 (10.0)	40 (10.0)	222 (55.5)	98 (24.5)	3.95 ± 0.86
5	Poor knowledge of project management and control by consultants	6 (1.5)	88 (22.0)	46 (11.5)	198 (49.5)	62 (15.5)	3.56 ± 1.04
6	Materials selection and change in types and specifications during construction	6 (1.5)	62 (15.5)	24 (6.0)	189 (47.3)	119 (29.8)	3.88 ± 1.05
7	Mistakes or discrepancies in documents specification issued by consultant	0 (0.0)	64 (16.0)	8 (2.0)	201 (50.2)	127 (31.8)	3.98 ± 0.99

8	Incomplete design prior to estimation	0 (0.0)	82 (20.5)	28 (7.0)	147 (36.8)	143 (35.8)	3.88 ± 1.11
9	Cash flow and financial difficulties faced by contractors in TETFund projects	4 (1.0)	32 (8.0)	22 (5.5)	223 (55.8)	119 (29.8)	4.05 ± 0.87
10	Improper planning and scheduling by contractor	0 (0.0)	65 (16.3)	21 (5.3)	197 (49.3)	117 (29.3)	3.92 ± 0.99
11	Frequent breakdown of construction equipment on site	6 (1.5)	84 (21.0)	59 (14.8)	201 (50.2)	50 (12.5)	3.51 ± 1.01
12	Poor understanding and interpretation of design and specification	6 (1.5)	80 (20.0)	36 (9.0)	209 (52.3)	69 (17.3)	3.64 ± 1.03
13	Variations, insufficient and improper detailing	4 (1.0)	40 (10.0)	8 (2.0)	285 (70.5)	66 (16.5)	3.92 ± 0.82
14	Poor contract coordination	0 (0.0)	20 (5.0)	43 (10.8)	280 (70.0)	57 (14.2)	3.94 ± 0.67
15	Unexpected inflation/material price escalation	0 (0.0)	34 (8.5)	28 (7.0)	163 (40.8)	175 (43.8)	4.19 ± 0.90
16	Irregular release of funds	0 (0.0)	10 (2.5)	38 (9.5)	251 (62.7)	101 (25.3)	4.11 ± 0.66

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 1 shows that management of TETFund projects is affected by lack of due diligence in prequalification of consultants at the early stage as indicated by a high mean response value of 4.23 greater than the criterion mean of 3, and a standard deviation of 0.55 indicating low variability of response. Other risk factors TETFund management includes Change in the scope of the project (3.59), Poor information flow between parties (4.04), lack of coordination at pre-contract stage (3.95), Poor knowledge of project management and control by consultants (3.56), Materials selection and change in types and specifications during construction (3.88), Mistakes or discrepancies in documents specification issued by consultant (3.98), Incomplete design prior to estimation (3.88), Cash flow and financial difficulties faced by contractors in TETFund projects (4.05), Improper planning and scheduling by contractor (3.92), Frequent breakdown of construction equipment on site (3.51), Poor understanding and interpretation of design and specification (3.64), Variations, insufficient and improper detailing (3.92), Poor contract coordination (3.94), Unexpected inflation/material price escalation (4.19) and Irregular release of funds (4.11).

Data analysis for objective two:

Table 2: Analysis of Objective Four: TETFUND Project Management Outcomes

	<i>Never</i>	<i>Less likely</i>	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>Likely</i>	<i>Most likely</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>
<i>How often do time overrun on TETFund projects occur?</i>	1 (0.3)	75 (18.8)	246 (61.5)	57 (14.2)	21 (5.3)	3.06 ± 0.74
<i>How often do cost overrun on TETFund projects occur?</i>	31 (7.8)	67 (16.8)	172 (43.0)	41 (10.3)	89 (22.3)	3.23 ± 1.19
<i>How often is completion period achieved?</i>	2 (0.5)	66 (16.5)	126 (31.5)	98 (24.5)	108 (27.0)	3.61 ± 1.07
<i>How often does dispute occur on TETFund projects?</i>	10 (0.0)	176 (44.0)	214 (53.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2.51 ± 0.55
<i>How often do abandonment occur on TETFund projects?</i>	46 (11.5)	175 (43.8)	103 (25.8)	76 (19.0)	0 (0.0)	2.52 ± 0.93
<i>How often do litigation occur on TETFund projects?</i>	70 (17.5)	237 (59.3)	51 (12.8)	42 (10.5)	0 (0.0)	2.16 ± 0.84

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 2 shows that time overrun is likely to occur on TETFund projects as indicated by high mean response of 3.06 greater than the criterion mean of 3 and a standard deviation of 0.74 indicating low variability of response. Similarly, cost overrun is likely to occur on TETFund projects as indicated by high mean response value of 3.23. Completion period is likely to be achieved on TETFund projects (3.61). Dispute (2.51), abandonment (2.52) and Litigation (2.16) is less likely to occur on TETFund projects as indicated by low mean response less than the criterion mean of 3.

Test of Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: Risk factors have a significant impact on the management outcomes of TETfund building projects in SouthEast Nigeria

Table 3: Impact of Design Development Risk on Management Outcomes of TETfund Projects

	R	R ²	B	P value
Time overrun	0.069	0.005	0.051	0.168
Cost overrun	0.041	0.002	-0.030	0.415
Project completion	0.037	0.001	-0.027	0.465
Dispute	0.056	0.003	-0.042	0.263
Abandonment	0.150	0.022	-0.111	0.003
Litigation	0.233	0.054	-0.173	< 0.001

Source: SPSS Computation, 2023.

Table 3 shows that poor design development risk has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of abandonment (p = 0.003, B = -0.111). Similarly, poor documentation has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of litigation (p < 0.001, B = -0.173).

Table 4: Impact of Employer change Risk on Management Outcomes of TETfund Projects

	R	R ²	B	P value
Time overrun	0.040	0.002	0.047	0.430
Cost overrun	0.070	0.006	-0.091	0.130
Project completion	0.067	0.005	0.080	0.180
Dispute	0.089	0.008	0.107	0.074
Abandonment	0.149	0.022	-0.178	0.003
Litigation	0.285	0.081	-0.340	< 0.001

Source: SPSS Computation, 2023.

Table 4 shows that the employer change risk has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of abandonment (p = 0.003, B = -0.178). Similarly, employer change risk has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of litigation (p < 0.001, B = -0.340).

Table 5: Impact of planning risk on management outcomes of TETfund projects

	R	R ²	B	P value
Time overrun	0.068	0.005	0.073	0.174
Cost overrun	0.003	0.000	-0.003	0.953
Project completion	0.038	0.001	0.040	0.454
Dispute	0.153	0.023	-0.164	0.002
Abandonment	0.172	0.030	-0.184	0.001
Litigation	0.354	0.126	-0.378	< 0.001

Source: SPSS Computation, 2023.

Table 5 shows that poor planningrisk has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of dispute (p = 0.002, B = -0.164), abandonment (p = 0.001, B = -0.184) and litigation (p < 0.001, B = -0.378).

Table 6: Impact of Construction Risk Factor on Management Outcomes of TETfund Projects

	R	R ²	B	P value
Time overrun	0.046	0.002	-0.025	0.357
Cost overrun	0.069	0.005	-0.038	0.167
Project completion	0.008	0.000	-0.004	0.874
Dispute	0.234	0.055	-0.128	< 0.001
Abandonment	0.039	0.002	-0.022	0.431
Litigation	0.268	0.072	-0.147	< 0.001

Source: SPSS Computation, 2023.

Table 6 shows that poor construction risk factor has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of dispute ($p < 0.001$, $B = -0.128$) and litigation ($p < 0.001$, $B = -0.147$).

Table 7: Impact offinancial and economic risk (employer other risk) on management outcomes of TETfund projects

	R	R ²	B	P value
Time overrun	0.157	0.025	-0.146	0.002
Cost overrun	0.021	0.000	-0.019	0.676
Project completion	0.024	0.001	-0.022	0.638
Dispute	0.250	0.063	-0.232	< 0.001
Abandonment	0.107	0.011	-0.099	0.032
Litigation	0.158	0.025	-0.147	0.001

Source: SPSS Computation, 2023.

Table 7 shows that financial and economic risk has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of project time overrun ($p = 0.002$, $B = -0.146$), dispute ($p < 0.001$, -0.232), Abandonment ($p = 0.032$, $B = -0.099$) and litigation ($p = 0.001$, $B = -0.147$).

Table 8: Impact of environmental and economic risk factors on management outcomes of TETfund projects

	R	R ²	B	P value
Time overrun	0.330	0.109	-0.276	< 0.001
Cost overrun	0.131	0.017	-0.109	0.009
Project completion	0.154	0.024	-0.128	0.002
Dispute	0.048	0.002	-0.040	0.343
Abandonment	0.182	0.033	-0.152	< 0.001
Litigation	0.251	0.063	-0.210	< 0.001

Source: SPSS Computation, 2023.

Table 8 shows that environmental and economic risk factors (e.g., inflation) has a significant negative impact on TETfund project management outcome in terms of project time overrun ($p < 0.001$, $B = -0.276$), project Cost overrun ($p = 0.009$, $B = -0.109$), project completion ($p = 0.002$, $B = -0.128$), Abandonment ($p < 0.001$, $B = -0.152$) and litigation ($p < 0.001$, $B = -0.210$).

Decision Rule

Since the significant value (p value) of the test statistic is less than 0.05 level of significance for at least one of the items tested, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternative accepted. Therefore, risk factors have a significant impact on the management outcomes of TETfund building projects in SouthEast Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 itemized the risk factors affecting the management of TETFund projects in South East, Nigeria, with due diligence in prequalification of consultants at the early stage as indicated by a high mean response value of 4.23 greater than the criterion mean of 3 and a standard deviation of 0.55 indicating low variability of response. Other risk factors TETFund management includes change in scope of project (3.59), poor information flow between parties (4.04), lack of coordination at pre-contract stage (3.95), poor knowledge of project management and control by consultants (3.95), materials selection and change in types and specifications during construction (3.88), mistakes or discrepancies in documents and specifications issued by consultants during construction (3.98), incomplete design prior to estimate (3.88), cash flow and financial difficulties faced by contractors in TETFund projects (4.05), improper planning and scheduling by contractor (3.92), frequent breakdown of construction equipment on site (3.51), poor understanding and interpretation of design and specification (3.64), variation, insufficient and improper detailing (3.92), poor contract coordination (3.94), unexpected inflation/material price escalation (4.19) and irregular release of funds (4.11).

Conclusion

This study sought to analyse the risk factors mitigating against TETFund building projects completion in Enugu, Anambra, Imo all in South East, Nigeria with a view to providing policy framework for TETFund project management outcomes. The understanding of these risk factors and their pattern of factors affecting the management of TETFund building projects in South East, Nigeria would help to cushion the challenges of mitigating them. This study has identified and assessed some important risks to TETFund building project delivery. This could be used as part of invitation to tender where each tenderer will be required to indicate how they intend to solve the problems during the construction phase of a TETFund building project. Client and project stakeholders should also note that taking responsibility for a risk will naturally have influence on pricing and the party taking responsibility of the risk. Therefore, to achieve value for money on TETFund objectives on TETFund building and projects, project team need to agree on acceptable risk allocation and mitigation method before the contract is awarded. At the same time, all necessary financial and material resources should be provided by TETFund to enable the risk response/mitigation to be implemented.

Recommendations

In assessing and mitigating construction and financial projects on behalf of TETFund projects, early involvement of competent consultants should help to reduce the cost of contract overrun and time overrun in TETFund building projects. The consultants should have advised TETFund on appropriate procurement rout to minimize the level of TETFund exposure to both construction and financial risk associated with TETFund building project in Nigeria.

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